

SPENDED IN THE MAIN TYPES OF SPORTS POWER CONSUMPTION

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Abstract. All sports are traditionally divided into 4 groups: low physical activity (chess, checkers); type of short-term but significant loads (acrobatics, gymnastics, equestrian sport, shooting, fencing, running up to 300 m, weightlifting); type of large volume and regular loading (running 400-3000 m, wrestling, swimming, sports games, multi-wrestling); long-load type (alpinism, 10,000 m run and marathon, bicycle race, rowing, skiing, walking sports).

Keywords: daily power consumption, daily ration, amount.

In the second group, energy consumption is not so high, but there are differences in the need for nutrients. For example, a weightlifter needs protein first, but also a sufficient amount of fat to provide energy to the body. Weight is important for acrobats and equestrians, so their diet is planned to avoid weight gain.

In the third group, it is necessary to provide material for muscle growth and at the same time to have a good glycogen reserve, since it has the nature of effort. In sports with a weight category, weight gain is limited.

In the fourth group, first of all, endurance is important, and the need for carbohydrates suddenly increases. Of course, it contains some fat, primarily unsaturated fats as a source of energy.

The next type of sport is period sport. This group of sports includes cycling, running at different distances, rowing. In hygiene, the term "rational nutrition" has been accepted, which means nutrition based on science, which fully meets the needs in terms of quality and quantity of food. An athlete's energy and nutrient needs depend on the type of sport and the amount of work performed, including skill level, mood and personal habits. The daily energy expenditure of athletes of different specialties is different: in the type of activity with little physical load (chess, checkers) it is 2800-3200 kcal for men and 2600-3000 kcal for women. In a short-term but high-intensity sport (acrobatics, gymnastics, jumping on a trampoline, diving, shooting, weightlifting, figure skating, etc.), energy consumption is 3500-4000 kcal for men and 3000-4000 kcal for women. Daily energy consumption in sports such as running 400 and 1500 m, boxing, wrestling, swimming, multi-sport, sports games, modern pentathlon is 4500-5500 kcal for men, 4000-5000 kcal for women. Finally, in the type of sports associated with long and sharp physical loads (alpinism, 10,000 m running, road cycling, rowing, cross-country skiing, skating, marathon, walking sports), the maximum daily energy expenditure for men is 5,500-6,500 kcal. and for women - 6000 kcal. In order to maintain high performance in sports, the body needs not only the right amount, but also optimal nutrients for digestion. The balanced nutrition formula is interconnected according to protein: fat: carbohydrates: = 14:30:56. To calculate the daily ration, it is necessary to know the energy coefficient of the main nutrients oxidized in the body: 1 g of oxidized protein gives 4.1 kcal, 1 g of fat gives 9.3 kcal, 1 g of carbohydrates gives 4.1 kcal. Now it is not difficult to calculate the amount of basic nutrients (g) for the daily diet. So, at 4000 kcal, the caloric content of the diet is 137 g due to proteins (560 kcal), 130 g due to fats (1200 kcal), and 546 g to carbohydrates (2240 kcal). (The calculation was taken for men with a body weight of 70 kg, for women with a body weight of 60 kg)., metabolic processes increase due to tension in the physical and mental level of athletes, which is called "metabolic stress". In such conditions,

the positive effect of food on the athlete's body depends not only on the amount of energy and nutrients consumed, but also on the full compliance with the rules of nutrition coordinated as a result of in-depth research, especially the differential selection of adequate forms of nutrition during intense training, preparation for competitions and during the recovery period of metabolic processes in various sports. need It is very important to use nutritional factors for specific types of metabolic processes, especially to perform certain sports loads, to increase muscle mass, to increase strength and endurance, as well as to choose adequate rates of food consumption.

The lack of protein in the diet of 7-10-year-old children is 16.3% in the winter-spring season, and 22.6% in the summer-autumn season; In most cases, the deficiency refers to proteins in animal products, which is mainly due to very low consumption of meat products, fish and dairy products.

Nutritional value of food products of 7-10-year-old children who play chess and checkers

Nutrient name	Hygie nik meor , g	Winter-spring season		Summer-autumn season	
		abs., g	Norm in %	abs., g	to % norm
Daily power consumption	2400	1966.6 ± 29,7	81.9	1839.4±32.4	76.6
Total proteins , g	80.5	67.4±9.7	83.7	62.3±11.4	77.4
Of this animal protein	49	33.3±4.6	68.0	29.5±4.9	60.2
fats , g	80	55.1±6.2	68.9	46.7±5.3	58.4
carbonated water , g	340	317.5±11.1	93.4	308.9±12.3	90.9
Calcium, m k g	1100	741.2±15.8	67.4	729.5±17.1	66.3
Phosphorus, m k g	1650	1109.6±20.4	67.2	1059.6±18.9	64.2
Magnesium, m k g	250	231.3±9.7	92.5	220.1±8.8	88.0
Vitamin C, mg	60	49.6±6.7	82.7	58.0±7.7	96.7
Vitamin A, mcg	700	212.6±11.7	30.4	162.1±10.4	23.2
Vitamin V ₁ , mg	1.2	1.09±0.03	90.8	1.06±0.02	88.3
Vitamin v ₂ , mg	1.4	1.33±0.04	95.0	1.27±0.03	90.7
Vitamin RR, mg	15	13.2±1.9	88.0	13.0±2.5	86.7

One of the important aspects of modern research in sports medicine is the study of tools and methods that contribute to the restoration of sports performance. One of the medically important aspects is the organization of rational nutrition depending on the type of sport, which helps to restore the working capacity of athletes during intense training and competitions. Distribution and assimilation of nutrients in the body is determined by factors such as rest, activity, level of fatigue, nutritional state (duration of hunger, digestive activity, effect of nutrition, post-adaptation state). The importance of nutrition in sports is very great, and the nutrition factor is

important in regulating metabolism. The rational use of food products helps to achieve effective results from training, increase muscle mass, increase body strength, and accelerate recovery.

CONCLUSION.

However, not all coaches and athletes have the basic knowledge of nutrition, as a result of which athletes determine the wrong way to eat. It is wrong to put lipstick on this or that food product, and it is impossible to pay all attention to it, but the importance of the athlete's diet should not be forgotten.

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